

Collinsella is associated with cumulative inflammatory burden in an established rheumatoid arthritis cohort

Patricia Ruiz-Limón^{a,b,d,1}, Natalia Mena-Vázquez^{a,c,1}, Isabel Moreno-Indias^{a,b,d,*}, Sara Manrique-Arija^{a,c,e}, Jose Manuel Lisbona-Montañez^{a,c,e}, Laura Cano-García^{a,c}, Francisco J. Tinahones^{a,b,d}, Antonio Fernández-Nebro^{a,c,e}

^a Instituto de Investigación Biomédica de Málaga y Plataforma en Nanomedicina-IBIMA Plataforma BIONAND, 29010 Málaga, Spain

^b Unidad de Gestión Clínica de Endocrinología y Nutrición, Hospital Clínico Virgen de la Victoria, 29010 Málaga, Spain

^c UGC de Reumatología, Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga, 29009 Málaga, Spain

^d CIBER Fisiopatología de la Obesidad y Nutrición (CIBEROBN), Instituto de Salud Carlos III, 28029 Madrid, Spain

^e Departamento de Medicina. Universidad de Málaga, 29010 Málaga, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Gut microbiota
Inflammation
Rheumatoid arthritis
Collinsella
Cumulative inflammatory burden

ABSTRACT

Objective: To analyze the gut microbiota of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) according to disease activity.

Methods: An observational cross-sectional study of 110 patients with RA and 110 age- and sex-matched controls was performed. Patients were classified according to the disease activity (DAS28 \geq 3.2 or DAS28 < 3.2). Clinical and epidemiological variables were included. The gut microbiota was analyzed using 16S rRNA sequencing and bioinformatics analysis based on QIIME and PICRUST. A multivariate analysis was performed to identify factors associated with inflammatory activity.

Results: The mean DAS28 indicated remission/low inflammatory activity in 71 patients (64.5 %) and moderate/high activity in 39 (35.5 %) during follow-up. Alpha and beta diversity analysis revealed differences in gut microbiota between the 3 study groups. In the moderate/high activity RA, we observed a significant change in the abundance of genera compared with the other groups. The abundance of *Collinsella* and *Bifidobacterium* was increased in RA patients compared with controls. The metabolic profile of gut microbiota was characterized by differences in pathways related to Biosynthesis, Generation of Precursor Metabolites/Energy, and Degradation/Utilization/Assimilation between the 3 groups. The factors associated with cumulative inflammatory activity in RA were age (OR [95 % CI], 1.065 [1.002–1.131]), obesity (OR [95% CI], 3.829 [1.064–8.785]), HAQ score (OR [95% CI], 2.729 [1.240–5.009]), and expansion of the genus *Collinsella* (OR [95% CI], 3.000 [1.754–9.940]).

Conclusions: The composition of gut microbiota differed between patients with RA and moderate/high activity, patients with remission/low activity, and controls. The genus *Collinsella*, age, obesity, and physical function were associated with cumulative inflammatory burden in RA.

1. Introduction

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by persistent synovitis, bone erosion, and functional disability. While the exact cause of RA is unknown, it is thought to result from the interaction between genetic, environmental, hormonal, and immunopathologic factors [1]. It is believed that a loss of local immune tolerance occurs first, distant to the joints, which spreads to other systems [2]. Data from recent studies suggest that the first stages in the development

of RA result from exposure of the mucosal surfaces where the microbiota and a large number of immune cells are located to environmental factors [3]. Diet and intestinal microbiota modify factors that can considerably affect the intestinal barrier, functional integrity, and regulation of permeability [4]. Antioxidants, lactobacilli, fiber, omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamins, and gut microbiota, influence the anti-inflammatory effects of the diet in RA patients [5,6].

Data on intestinal microbiota and RA in humans suggest that affected patients have different grades of dysbiosis and reduced microbial

* Correspondence to: Instituto de Investigación Biomédica de Málaga (IBIMA), 29010 Málaga, Spain;

E-mail address: isabel.moreno@ibima.eu (I. Moreno-Indias).

¹ These authors share the first authorship.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioph.2022.113518>

Received 19 June 2022; Received in revised form 1 August 2022; Accepted 3 August 2022

Available online 6 August 2022

0753-3322/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Masson SAS. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

diversity compared with controls [7–9]. Studies point to chronic inflammation of the intestine characterized by a change in intestinal microbiota from a symbiotic to a dysbiotic microbial community. While the microorganisms identified differ depending on the study, alterations in microbiota can vary from one population to another owing to factors such as the age, sex, genotype, diet, and geography of the host [10]. Intestinal dysbiosis and specific bacterial lineages are also thought to be associated with clinical factors in RA such as levels of immunoglobulins, anticitrullinated peptide antibodies (ACPA), and rheumatoid factor (RF) [1]. A pilot study by our group in patients with established RA found dysbiosis to be characterized by expansion of rare and harmful lineages, such as *Collinsella*, *Enterococcus*, and *Sedimentibacter*, together with a reduction in other widely extended lineages in healthy individuals and inducers of intestinal homeostasis, such as *Dorea* and *Sarcina*. Furthermore, *Collinsella aerofaciens* is associated with factors involved in the severity of RA, such as smoking and high ACPA levels [8].

Some studies have evaluated the association between intestinal dysbiosis, prognosis and inflammation of RA [11–13]. In this sense, Zhang et al. [13] found an overabundance of *Lactobacillus salivarius* in patients with isolated determination of 28-joint Disease Activity Score with erythrocyte sedimentation rate (DAS28-ESR) > 5.1 compared with those with reduced inflammatory activity; and Picchianti-Diamanti et al. [14] showed an independent association between DAS28 and *Euryarchaeota* at the phylum level and *Erysipelotrichi* at the class level. However, the association between intestinal dysbiosis and cumulative inflammatory burden since the diagnosis of RA has not been directly addressed in the literature. Consequently, the objective of the present study was [1] to characterize the intestinal microbiota profile of patients with established RA, [2] to describe the cumulative inflammatory burden from disease diagnosis in patients with established RA, and [3] to investigate whether there is an association between intestinal dysbiosis and cumulative inflammatory burden in an established rheumatoid arthritis cohort.

2. Patients and methods

2.1. Study design and participants

The population of this nested case-control study comprised 110 RA patients and 110 healthy age- and sex-matched donors from the same geographical area. Patients with RA were selected from a cohort of incident cases of RA recruited between 2007 and 2011 and followed prospectively until today. RA patients were classified according to the 2010 criteria of the American College of Rheumatology/European League against Rheumatism [15], including seropositivity for rheumatoid factor (RF) and/or anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs). All patients were diagnosed and treated during the 12 months following the onset of their disease. Only subjects 16 years or older were selected. The exclusion criteria were the presence of inflammatory, autoimmune, or rheumatic diseases other than RA (except for secondary Sjögren's syndrome), diabetes, or any non-controlled general condition. We also excluded patients and controls with extreme diets, those exposed to antibiotic therapy (current or previous 3 months), those taking probiotic agents, and those who had started any new treatment.

All participants provided their written informed consent before entering the study. The study was conducted according to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Málaga (Project identification code 4/2016, P19).

2.2. Laboratory and clinical variables

All the participants were given an appointment at the clinic, where their data were recorded in a database on the index date (ie, the date on which participants were included in the study). Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and treatment-related data were recorded by a

rheumatologist. Demographic variables included age (in years), sex, and race. We also collected conventional cardiovascular risk-related variables, as follows: smoking (active, ex-smoker, never), obesity (body mass index >30) [16], arterial hypertension $\geq 140/90$ mmHg or current antihypertensive medication [17], diabetes diagnosed according to the criteria of the American Diabetes Association [18], and a personal history of cardiovascular disease.

The characteristics of patients with RA included the date of onset of the disease, time with the disease (calculated from diagnosis to cut-off), and the following laboratory data: RF (reference value, 20 U/ml; high titer, >60 U/ml), ACPA (reference value, 10 U/ml; high value, >340 U/ml), C-reactive protein (mg/dl), and ESR (mm/h). We evaluated cumulative inflammatory activity in all patients using the DAS28-ESR (range, 0–9.4) [19] at each visit since the initiation of the cohort [18]. In this manner, our population was estratified according to their DAS28-ESR: high activity was defined as a score >5.1, moderate activity as 3.2–5.1, low activity as 2.6–3.2, and remission as ≤ 2.6 . However, considering the good disease control of our patients, we categorized them for the current analysis into having a moderate/high activity (DAS28-ESR ≥ 3.2) and remission/low activity (DAS28-ESR <3.2) [20–23]. We also took into account variables associated with severity such as the presence of radiologic erosions and assessed physical function using the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) throughout the disease course [18]. We recorded treatment with conventional synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (csDMARDs) and biologic DMARDs (bDMARDs).

2.3. Sample collection and DNA extraction

Peripheral venous blood samples were collected after an overnight fast. Fecal samples were refrigerated immediately and transported to the laboratory, where they were stored at -80°C for subsequent analysis. DNA was extracted from 200 mg of stool sample using the QIAamp DNA Stool Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA concentrations and purity were determined using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Nanodrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA). After extraction, DNA was stored at -20°C until further processing.

2.4. 16S sequencing

The Ion 16 S Metagenomics Kit and Ion Plus Fragment Library Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., Waltham, MA, USA) were used to prepare the amplicon library, as previously described [8].

Emulsion PCR and sequencing of the amplicon libraries were performed on an Ion 530 chip (Ion 530™ Chip Kit) using the Ion Chef System and Torrent S5™ system, respectively (Ion 510™/520™/530™ Kit-Chef, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.5. Bioinformatics Analysis

Base calling and run demultiplexing were performed using Torrent Suite™ Server software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), version 5.4.0, with default parameters for targeted 16 S sequencing (bead loading ≤ 30 , key signal ≤ 30 , and usable sequences ≤ 30). Quality sequences were further translated into amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) using DADA2 with adapted parameters for Ion Torrent data within the open-source Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology software (QIIME2, version 2019.10) [24], which was also used for diversity analysis with the diversity plugin. Alpha diversity indexes (observed-features and pi-euclidean) and weighted and unweighted UniFrac distance matrices were calculated. Taxonomic analysis was performed through clustering with VSEARCH and the reference base Greengenes version 13.8 at 97% identity. The Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States plugin

(PICRUSt2) [25] was used to predict metagenome function within QIIME2. MetaCyc pathways [26] were normalized within QIIME2 and further analyzed with STAMP [27].

2.6. Statistical analysis

A descriptive analysis was performed based on absolute frequencies and percentages for qualitative variables and the mean (standard deviation [SD]) or median (interquartile range [IQR]) for quantitative variables. The normality of the distribution was confirmed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Patients and controls were compared using the Pearson χ^2 test or the *t* test, as applicable. The χ^2 and ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis test (depending on normality) were applied to compare the main characteristics between 3 groups of patients: (I) patients with RA and moderate/high inflammatory activity; (II) patients with RA and remission/low inflammatory activity; and (III) controls. Finally, we ran a multivariate logistic regression model (dependent variable: moderate/high cumulative inflammatory activity) to identify variables that were independently associated with RA. The variables entered into the model were those that proved to be significant in the bivariate analysis and those that were of clinical interest.

In relation to the microbiome data, the statistical analysis was performed within QIIME2. Group differences in terms of alpha diversity were assessed using the Kruskal–Wallis test, whereas beta diversity was assessed using PERMANOVA. Differences in abundance between the groups studied were analyzed using the microbiome method ANCOM [28]. The W value was used to indicate the significance and its magnitude when the null hypothesis was rejected.

Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

3. Results

3.1. Characteristics of the study population

The study population consisted of 220 subjects, namely, 110 RA patients and 110 healthy controls. Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of patients and controls. Both groups were well balanced in terms of sex and age. However, RA patients more frequently presented obesity ($p = 0.027$) and had a personal history of cardiovascular disease ($p = 0.004$), with 16 % more ex-smokers than controls. RA patients also had higher levels of acute phase reactants and autoantibodies than controls.

Most of the patients were women (80 %) with a mean age of around 56 years. All patients were under treatment with DMARDs, 102/110 (92.7 %) were taking csDMARDs, and 42/110 (38.1 %) were taking bDMARDs, mostly anti-TNF. A total of 20/110 patients (18.2 %) were receiving corticosteroids.

During follow-up, DAS28-ESR indicated remission/low inflammatory activity (< 3.2) in 71 patients (64.5 %) and moderate/high activity in 39 (35.5 %). Table 2 shows the differences in clinical characteristics between patients with RA according to inflammatory activity and controls. Compared with RA patients with remission/low disease activity and controls, those with highly active RA had a greater frequency of smoking ($p = 0.006$), diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.048$), dyslipidemia ($p = 0.035$), obesity ($p = 0.009$), and personal history of cardiovascular disease (0.015). They also had higher levels of CRP ($p < 0.001$) and ESR ($p < 0.001$). Likewise, patients with RA and moderate/high activity presented a higher frequency of ACPA at high titers, as well as a higher HAQ score, than patients with RA and remission/low inflammatory activity.

3.2. Gut microbiota diversity in RA patients and controls

The gut microbiota of RA patients differed from that of healthy

Table 1

Baseline characteristics of patients with RA and controls.

Variable	RA n = 110	Controls n = 110	p-value
Epidemiological characteristics			
Age in years, median (IQR)	55.9 (49.3–64.4)	56.2 (48.3–65.3)	0.917
Female sex, n (%)	88 (80.0)	88 (80.0)	1.000
Caucasian race, n (%)	108 (98.2)	109 (99.1)	0.561
Smoking			
Never smoked, n (%)	47 (42.7)	68 (61.8)	0.004
Ex-smoker, n (%)	30 (27.3)	13 (11.8)	
Active smoker, n (%)	33 (30.0)	29 (26.4)	
Comorbid conditions			
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	28 (25.5)	25 (22.7)	0.636
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	6 (5.5)	2 (1.8)	0.150
Dyslipidemia, n (%)	25 (22.7)	21 (19.3)	0.530
Obesity (WHO), n (%)	40 (36.4)	25 (22.7)	0.027
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	18 (16.4)	5 (4.5)	0.004
Clinical and laboratory characteristics			
Time since diagnosis of RA, months, median (IQR)	93.2 (77.6–123.4)	–	–
Diagnostic delay, months, median (IQR)	8.1 (4.5–17.0)	–	–
Erosions, n (%)	68 (61.8)	–	–
RF > 10, n (%)	90 (81.8)	0 (0,0)	<0.001
ACPA > 20 U/ml, n (%)	88 (80.0)	0 (0,0)	<0.001
High ACPA > 340 U/ml, n (%)	36 (32.7)	0 (0,0)	<0.001
CRP (mg/dl), median (IQR)	2.9 (2.9–6.2)	2.9 (2.9–3.3)	<0.001
ESR (mm/h), median (IQR)	13.0 (8.0–21.0)	11.0 (6.0–16.0)	0.008
DAS28-ESR at cut-off, mean (\pm SD)	2.9 (1.0)	–	–
Remission/low activity, n (%)	69 (62.7)	–	–
Moderate/high activity, n (%)	41 (37.3)	–	–
DAS28-ESR, mean (\pm SD)	3.0 (0.7)	–	–
Remission/low activity, n (%)	71 (64.5)	–	–
Moderate/high activity, n (%)	39 (35.5)	–	–
HAQ at cut-off, median (IQR)	0.75 (0.1–1.2)	–	–
Average HAQ, median (IQR)	0.71 (0.3–0.9)	–	–
Conventional synthetic DMARDs, n (%)	102 (92.7)	–	–
Methotrexate, n (%)	79 (71.8)	–	–
Leflunomide, n (%)	12 (10.9)	–	–
Sulfasalazine, n (%)	13 (11.8)	–	–
Hydroxychloroquine, n (%)	9 (8.2)	–	–
Biologic DMARDs, n (%)	42 (38.1)	–	–
Anti-TNF- α , n (%)	32 (29.1)	–	–
Etanercept, n (%)	17 (15.3)	–	–
Adalimumab, n (%)	6 (5.5)	–	–
Infliximab, n (%)	4 (3.6)	–	–
Golimumab, n (%)	3 (2.7)	–	–
Certolizumab, n (%)	2 (1.8)	–	–
Tocilizumab, n (%)	7 (6.4)	–	–
Rituximab, n (%)	2 (1.8)	–	–
Tofacitinib, n (%)	1 (0.9)	–	–
Corticosteroids at cut-off, n (%)	20 (18.2)	–	–
Dose of corticosteroids at cut-off (mg/day), median (IQR)	5 (5.0–5.0)	–	–

Abbreviations: RA: rheumatoid arthritis; IQR: interquartile range; RF: rheumatoid factor; ACPA: anticitrullinated peptide antibody; CRP: C-reactive protein; ESR: erythrocyte sedimentation rate; DAS28-ESR (28-joint Disease Activity Score with ESR); SD: standard deviation; HAQ: Health Assessment Questionnaire; DMARD: disease-modifying antirheumatic drug; JAK: Janus kinase.

controls according to the dimensional principal coordinates analysis plots of UniFrac distances in their qualitative version (unweighted UniFrac distances, PERMANOVA, $p = 0.004$). A further classification according to inflammatory activity revealed differences in both interpretations (unweighted UniFrac distances [$p = 0.002$] and weighted UniFrac distances [$p = 0.001$]). Fig. 1B shows the clusterization of the different groups in their quantitative version (weighted UniFrac distances).

Alpha diversity analysis revealed significant differences in community richness (observed-features, $p = 0.002$) and homogeneity (pielou-

Table 2
Baseline characteristics of patients with RA according to inflammatory activity and controls.

Variable	RA moderate/high activity (n = 39)	RA remission/low activity (n = 71)	Controls (n = 110)	p-value
Epidemiologic characteristics				
Age in years, median (IQR)	59.6 (52.2–66.9)	54.6 (46.8–60.5)	56.2 (48.3–65.3)	0.277
Female sex, n (%)	29 (74.4)	59 (83.1)	88 (80.0)	0.552
Caucasian race, n (%)	39 (100.0)	69 (97.2)	109 (99.1)	0.405
BMI (kg/m ²), mean (SD)	30.0 (5.8)	27.5 (4.4)	27.1 (4.5)	0.004
Smoking				
Never smoked, n (%)	9 (23.1)	38 (53.5)	68 (61.8)	0.006
Ex-smoker, n (%)	15 (38.5)	15 (21.1)	13 (11.8)	
Active smoker, n (%)	15 (38.5)	18 (25.4)	29 (26.4)	
Comorbid conditions				
Arterial hypertension, n (%)	13 (33.3)	15 (21.1)	25 (22.7)	0.324
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	4 (10.3)	2 (2.8)	2 (1.8)	0.048
Dyslipidemia, n (%)	14 (35.9)	11 (15.5)	21 (19.3)	0.035
Obesity (WHO), n (%)	19 (48.7)	21 (29.6)	25 (22.7)	0.009
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	9 (23.1)	9 (12.6)	5 (4.5)	0.015
Clinical-laboratory characteristics				
Time since diagnosis of RA, months, median (IQR)	90.5 (79.2–109.7)	98.6 (77.6–113.9)	NR	0.178
Diagnostic delay, months, median (IQR)	8.9 (4.6–17.6)	8.1 (5.7–13.3)	NR	0.927
Erosions, n (%)	26 (66.7)	42 (59.2)	NR	0.438
RF > 10, n (%)	33 (84.6)	57 (80.3)	NR	0.573
ACPA > 20 U/ml, n (%)	31 (79.5)	57 (80.3)	NR	0.921
High ACPA > 340 U/ml, n (%)	20 (51.3)	16 (22.5)	NR	0.002
CRP (mg/dl), median (IQR)	4.9 (2.9–12.3)	2.9 (2.9–5.2)	2.9 (2.9–3.2)	<0.001
ESR (mm/h), median (IQR)	18.0 (10.0–26.0)	11.1 (7.5–18.0)	11.0 (6.0–16.0)	<0.001
HAQ at cut-off, median (IQR)	1.0 (0.6–1.3)	0.5 (0.0–1.0)	NR	0.004
Average HAQ, median (IQR)	0.8 (0.3–1.1)	0.5 (0.2–0.9)	NR	0.041
Conventional synthetic DMARDs, n (%)	36 (92.3)	66 (93.0)	NR	0.900
Methotrexate, n (%)	29 (74.4)	50 (70.4)	NR	0.661
Leflunomide, n (%)	3 (7.7)	9 (12.7)	NR	0.423
Sulfasalazine, n (%)	7 (17.9)	6 (8.5)	NR	0.140
Hydroxychloroquine, n (%)	2 (5.1)	7 (9.9)	NR	0.386
Biologic DMARDs, n (%)	17 (43.6)	25 (35.2)	NR	0.387
Anti-TNF-α, n (%)	13 (33.3)	19 (26.8)	NR	0.468
Anti-IL-6, n (%)	2 (5.1)	5 (7.6)	NR	0.694
Rituximab, n (%)	1 (2.6)	1 (1.4)	NR	0.664
JAK inhibitor, n (%)	1 (2.6)	0 (0.0)	NR	0.175
Corticosteroids at cut-off, n (%)	8 (20.5)	12 (16.9)	NR	0.639

Abbreviations RA: rheumatoid arthritis; IQR: interquartile range; BMI: body mass index; SD: standard deviation; RF: rheumatoid factor; ACPA: anticitrullinated peptide antibody; CRP: C-reactive protein; ESR: erythrocyte sedimentation rate; HAQ: Health Assessment Questionnaire; DMARD: disease-modifying antirheumatic drug; JAK: Janus kinase.

evenness, $p = 0.020$) between the 3 groups. Specifically, a significant difference was found in the moderate/high activity group, demonstrating a significant increase in homogeneity compared with the remission/low activity group (pielou-evenness, $p = 0.006$) and a

significant decrease in richness compared with both the control (observed features, $p = 0.009$) and remission/low activity groups (observed features, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 1A).

3.3. Differences in gut microbiota between groups

An ANCOM analysis was performed based on the differential abundance analysis of the study groups to understand intergroup changes in the gut microbiota. The moderate/high activity group showed a significantly decreased abundance in the *Firmicutes* phylum ($W=2$), as well as its family *Streptococcaceae* ($W=2$) compared with the other groups. The abundance of the *Actinobacteria* phylum ($W=4$), its family *Coriobacteriaceae* ($W=10$), and its genus *Collinsella* ($W=17$) were significantly increased in RA patients compared with controls. Significant differences between the 3 groups were observed for the minority bacterial taxa *Spirochaetes* ($W=2$), *Synergistetes* ($W=3$), and its genus *Synergistes* ($W=3$), as well as the family *EtOH8* ($W=5$) and an unknown genus of this family ($W=4$). The abundance of *Oxalobacteraceae* ($W=2$) and an unknown family of the order *RF32* ($W=3$) was significantly higher in controls than in RA patients (Fig. 2A and B). The most remarkable findings were observed at the genus level, as 18 genera changed significantly. Significant differences were observed between the 3 groups for the genera *Weissella* ($W=2$), *Eubacterium* ($W=3$), *Anaerotruncus* ($W=5$), *Mogibacterium* ($W=5$), unknown genus of class *TM7-3* ($W=2$), *rc4-4* ($W=2$), and *Succinatimonas* ($W=2$). *Bifidobacterium* ($W=2$) became more abundant in RA patients than in controls. *Alistipes* ($W=6$) became significantly more abundant in the moderate/high activity RA group than in the other groups. However, the genera *Veillonella* ($W=10$), *Dorea* ($W=3$), and *Coproccoccus* ($W=5$), as well as an unknown genus of the family *Lachnospiraceae* ($W=4$) and an unknown genus of the family *Erysipelotrichaceae* ($W=8$), became significantly less abundant in the moderate/high activity RA group than in the other groups. Furthermore, an unknown genus of the order *RF32* ($W=2$) became significantly more abundant in controls than in RA patients (Fig. 3).

3.4. Predicted metabolic profiles of gut microbiota

Metacyc pathway analysis was performed using PiCRUST2 to increase our understanding of the role of gut microbiota in each of the groups studied. A Kruskal-Wallis analysis showed that 60 pathways ($p < 0.05$) differed between the groups. These pathways belonged mainly to Biosynthesis, Generation of Precursor Metabolites and Energy, and Degradation/Utilization/Assimilation pathways. Specifically, the most relevant pathways were those involved in the biosynthesis of cobalamin (COBALSYN-PWY, PWY-6269 and PWY-5509), purine (PWY-6121, PWY-6122, PWY-6123, PWY-7234, PWY-6277) and amino acid (HISTSYN-PWY, PWY-2942, PWY-5097) which were enriched in moderate/high activity RA group, while a decreased was observed in routes involved in the biosynthesis of the heme (HEME-BIOSYNTHESIS-II, HEMESYN2-PWY, PWY-5918, PWY5920, PWY0-1415) and in L-alanine biosynthesis (PWY0-1061). Additionally, moderate/high activity RA group was enriched in pathways involved in generation of precursor metabolites and energy such as fermentation of short-chain fatty acids (PWY-6588, FERMENTATION-PWY, PWY-5100, PWY-5676) and in pathways of degradation/utilization/assimilation such as purine (PWY-5695), while amino acid degradation (LEU-DEG2-PWY, TYRFUMCAT-PWY) was reduced in moderate/high activity RA group (Fig. 4 and Supplemental table S1). However, although the moderate/high activity group seems to show a more dissimilar pattern, the absence of marked differences between groups precludes us from establishing a possible mechanism of action.

3.5. Factors associated with inflammatory activity in RA

Table 3 shows the results of multivariate logistic regression analysis for the dependent variable mean moderate/high inflammatory activity

Fig. 1. Gut microbiota diversity. A) Alpha diversity indexes: piéou-evenness and observed-features among different groups were compared. Values are mean \pm SD. Kruskal–Wallis test, * $p < 0.05$ moderate/high activity RA patients vs. remission/low activity RA patients; \$ $p < 0.05$ moderate/high activity RA patients vs. control. B) Principal coordinates analysis plot of weighted UniFrac distance of fecal bacterial communities. Statistical differences were observed between groups (PERMANOVA, $p < 0.05$). Green dots belong to the control; blue dots for remission/low activity RA patients and orange dots for moderate/high activity RA patients.

in patients with RA. Age, obesity (body mass index [BMI] ≥ 30 kg/m²), high HAQ score, and expansion of the *Collinsella* genus were independently associated with inflammatory activity in patients with RA. These factors account for approximately 35% of the variability in the presence of inflammation in these patients ($R^2 = 0.348$).

4. Discussion

In the present study, we evaluated the gut microbiota profile in patients with established RA and sex- and age-matched healthy controls in order to describe their differences, as well as their relationship with the inflammatory activity of RA. For this purpose, we used cumulative inflammatory burden, measured as the averaged DAS28-ESR since entry into a prospective baseline cohort. This variable could help detect better than one-time disease activity the impact of disease activity on the intestinal microbiota and the severity of RA [29]. According to this criterion, we observed that average rates of remission/low activity (DAS28-ESR < 3.2) had been maintained in 64.5 % of patients and moderate/high activity (DAS28-ESR ≥ 3.2) in 35.5 %.

The beta diversity analysis showed that gut microbiome populations differed according to the grade of inflammatory activity, as specified by the difference between the weighted UniFrac distances of the study groups. Especially relevant was the clusterization of the moderate/high

activity group with respect to the remission/low activity and control groups. The evenness index was significantly higher and richness significantly lower (observed-features index) in the moderate/high activity group than in the other groups. These alpha diversity results could indicate a low number of bacteria with marked differences between abundances in the moderate/high activity group. Lower microbial diversity in RA patients than in controls has been reported elsewhere and is characterized by the expansion of some bacteria at the expense of others [23–25]. Moreover, a decrease in richness was also found in HLA mice that were prone to develop RA accompanied by an increase in inflammatory cytokines [26]. However, this reduction in richness has not yet been associated with poorer control of maintained inflammatory activity in patients with RA.

Interestingly, obesity (BMI > 30) was more frequent in RA patients than in controls, and within RA patients, obesity was independently associated with high inflammatory activity. These data support the findings of other studies showing that higher BMI increases the risk of RA [30]. However, other factors associated with a higher cumulative inflammatory load in RA included age and the physical function measured according to the HAQ. Various studies have shown that elderly RA patients presented more serious forms of the disease, with more pronounced inflammatory activity, worse physical function, and comorbidities, as well as a lower probability of complete remission

Fig. 2. Taxa that significantly changed between the study groups at different taxonomic levels. A) At the phylum level. B) At the family level. ANCOM method, $p < 0.05$. Values are mean \pm SD.

[31–33]. In the study by Chen et al. [34], the authors reported higher levels of inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) that were positively correlated with the DAS28-ESR in RA patients aged >65 years. The HAQ is the most widely used measurement of physical function in RA [35], and more impaired physical function has been associated with higher inflammatory activity and mortality [36–38]. In this sense, Norton et al. studied two large RA cohorts to determine the progression of HAQ over time. Functional disability was associated mainly with early-stage disease and with radiographic joint damage in patients with established RA [36]. Indeed, the mean cumulative HAQ score has made it easier to establish an association with cumulative inflammatory activity. Pan et al. [37] observed that the mean HAQ score during the 3-year follow-up of RA patients was independently associated with a higher DAS28.

According to the differential abundance analysis, levels of the *Coriobacteriaceae* family and its genus *Collinsella* were higher in RA patients than in controls. This result is in accordance with other studies, where the abundance of *Collinsella* was associated with the pathogenesis of RA [8,11,12,39]. It was also consistent with the findings of a pilot study with patients similar to those of our previous study, where we reported an association between smoking, ACPA levels, and abundance of *Collinsella* [8]. Moreover, we also observed a higher abundance of the microbial genes related to the arginine-deiminase activity associated with the genus *Collinsella*, suggesting a possible role for this activity in protein citrullination and development of RA [8]. Other mechanisms have been proposed. For example, *Collinsella* could affect the inflammatory process in RA by increasing the expression of IL17A, ROR α , CXCL1, and CXCL5, thus leading to altered neutrophil chemotaxis [40], an increase in NF κ B1, and activation of inflammatory pathways [41]. In fact, our multivariate analysis revealed an increase in *Collinsella* in the RA group, with moderate/high activity maintained over time, indicating its involvement in the inflammatory process of the disease.

RA patients were also characterized by an increase in the level of *Bifidobacterium*, which played an important role in the stimulation of the immune system and barrier effects and was associated with a wide range of beneficial health effects [42]. While our findings contradict the literature to a certain extent, Asquith et al. observed an increase in

Bifidobacterium longum in patients with HLA-DRB1 RA-risk alleles [43], possibly indicating a more immunogenic environment in RA patients than in healthy controls. Finally, other minority phyla found to be increased in RA patients include *Spirochaetes* and *Synergistetes*, both of which are associated with other autoimmune diseases. One study observed lower levels of *Synergistetes* in systemic lupus erythematosus [44], and another showed depleted levels of these phyla in primary Sjögren's syndrome [45]. On the other hand, levels of *Oxalobacteraceae* and unknown family of order RF32 were higher in the control group than in RA patients. Consistent with our findings, Kurilshikov et al. reported that an increase in the *Oxalobacteraceae* family exerted a protective effect on RA in a large-scale association analysis of 24 population-based cohorts [46]. However, further research is necessary to know more about the role of these minority bacteria in the etiology and pathogenesis of RA.

As for inflammatory activity, interesting associations discovered in the moderate/high activity group included the increase in the genus *Alistipes*, which has been involved in liver fibrosis, colorectal cancer, and cardiovascular disease [47], as well as in the core microbiome of Hashimoto's thyroiditis, an autoimmune thyroid disease [48]. We also observed a decrease in the abundance of the genera *Veillonella*, *Dorea*, and *Coprococcus*. Gupta et al. [49] observed that inflammatory activity was lower in RA patients with a higher abundance of *Coprococcus*. On the other hand, an increase in the abundance of *Veillonella* and *Dorea* has previously been observed in RA patients compared with controls, although the association between this increase and inflammatory activity has not been previously addressed [8,39]. Other minor genera were also decreased in the moderate/high activity RA group, such as an unknown genus of the family *Lachnospiraceae* and an unknown genus of the family *Erysipelotrichaceae*. The family *Lachnospiraceae* is a major butyrate producer and was found to be decreased in untreated new-onset RA [50]. Furthermore, a species of *Erysipelotrichaceae* family was more abundant in RA patients who did not show clinical improvement [49]. Given that no data have been reported on the association between these bacteria and inflammatory activity, this warrants further investigation.

The specific characteristics of the gut microbiota profile in the

Fig. 3. Taxa that significantly changed between the study groups at the genus level. ANCOM method, $p < 0.05$. Values are mean \pm SD.

remission/low activity RA group included an increase in the abundance of *Streptococcaceae* compared with the other groups. Several studies have associated *Streptococcus*, a member of the *Streptococcaceae* family, with different host pathways, including RA [51], and has been related to different host pathways in each disease, suggesting that similar microbes can affect host pathophysiology in a disease-specific manner through regulation of different host genes [52]. In line with our findings, those of a study conducted on autoimmune thyroid disease showed that levels of *Streptococcaceae* and *Streptococcus* were higher in patients with Hashimoto’s thyroiditis than in those with Graves-Basedow’s disease [48]. However, the relationship between *Streptococcaceae* and the degree of inflammatory activity in RA has not been previously addressed, although the abundance of *Streptococcus* has been associated with the severity of effusion in knee joints [53]. Data are needed to determine whether the *Streptococcaceae* family is involved in the amelioration or deterioration of the inflammatory process within RA.

Finally, our microbial metabolism approach based on the inference of the metabolic pathways taken by the gut microbiota using PICRUSt2

indicates that, while no marked differences were found between the 3 groups studied, the main pathways implicated point to the role of intestinal permeability resulting from clusters of pathways, such as those associated with purine metabolism [54], fermentation of short-chain fatty acids [55], cobalamin biosynthesis [56], or heme group biosynthesis [57]. It is worth noting that impaired intestinal permeability has been already reported in RA [58], and more pronounced inflammation has been associated with higher intestinal permeability [59], mainly through increased bacterial lipopolysaccharides (endotoxemia) [60,61]. Consequently, although this assumption must be further explored using more reliable techniques, it is feasible that gut microbiota could influence the inflammatory activity of RA patients through the regulation of gut permeability.

Our study is subject to a series of limitations, the first being its cross-sectional nature. However, patients were from a prospective cohort of early-stage RA where all the data on inflammation were longitudinally collected based on a predesigned protocol. This explains the low frequency of missing data and the consistency of our results. We must also

Fig. 4. Predictive metabolic pathways by PICRUSt2. Heatmap representing mean values of significantly increasing or decreasing predicted metagenome pathways between the three groups. Kruskal Wallis test, $p < 0.05$.

Table 3

Logistic regression model for factors associated with cumulative moderate/high inflammatory activity in patients with RA.

Dependent variable	Predictor	OR	95% CI for B	p value
Cumulative inflammatory activity*	Age, years	1.065	1.002–1.131	0.043
	HAQ	2.729	1.240–5.009	0.013
	BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ²	3.829	1.064–8.785	0.004
	<i>Collinsella</i>	3.000	1.754–9.940	0.014

Abbreviations: OR: odds ratio; CI: confidence interval; HAQ: Health Assessment Questionnaire; BMI: body mass index.

*Inflammatory activity: cumulative moderate/high inflammatory activity (DAS28-ESR ≥ 3.2).

Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.348$

Variables included in the equation: sex, age, erosions, HAQ, BMI ≥ 30 , ACPA, gMogibacterium, gCollinsella, fStreptococcaceae, gSynergistes, gCoproccoccus, gVeillonella, gAlistipes, gDorea.

take into account the role of factors that potentially affect gut microbiota and RA, such as genetics, diet, stress, and drugs. However, the inclusion criteria of the study were strict, prohibiting previous dietary or treatment modifications and intake of probiotics and antibiotics. In this sense, all RA patients were being treated with DMARDs, and although these drugs are thought to act on gut microbiota, it would be unethical not to treat patients with established disease and evidence of inflammatory activity. Likewise, subjects were selected from the same geographical area, and this might not account for possible geographical diversity; however, the fact that the subjects were from the same geographical area allows for a homogeneous sample of the population in terms of epidemiological and microbiological characteristics, and that our results can be extrapolated to the reference population. The use of 16S rRNA sequencing prevented us from obtaining a full range of data

that could be provided by other techniques, such as shotgun sequencing and metatranscriptomics. Furthermore, the biochemical pathways of the gut microbiome point to functional potential, that is, functional possibilities inferred from genetic content.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, we addressed the association between gut microbiota in RA patients and inflammatory activity. Despite the multiple differences found between the groups studied and in accordance with multiple previous reports, the genus *Collinsella* seems to have an important role within established RA and its severity. Moreover, other factors such as age, obesity, and physical function were associated with higher inflammatory activity in RA patients. Our results pave the way for new approaches in the fight against RA. Further research should investigate how these factors might influence onset and maintenance of inflammation in RA patients.

Funding

This work was supported by Instituto Salud Carlos III (grants cofunded by ERDF) (PI18/00824). The research groups belong to the "Centros de Investigación en Red" (CIBERobn), of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III. The authors thank the Metagenomic Platform of the Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Fisiopatología de la Obesidad y la Nutrición, CIBERobn, Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII), Spain, and, especially, Pablo Rodríguez. PRL was supported by a "Sara Borrell" postdoctoral contract (CD19/00216) from the ISCIII-Madrid (Spain), cofunded by the Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional-FEDER. IMI was supported by the "Miguel Servet Type II" program (CPII21/00013) of the ISCIII-Madrid (Spain). "Ayuda de Garantía Juvenil 2020" of the University of Malaga, Spain (SNGJ5Y6-12).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

PRL: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. NMV: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft. IMI: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision. SMA: Investigation, Methodology, JMLM: Investigation. LCG: Investigation. FJT: Conceptualization, Supervision. AFN: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

FERBT2021- The authors thank the Spanish Foundation of Rheumatology for providing medical writing/editorial assistance during the preparation of the manuscript. Some of the materials used in the graphical abstract were from Servier Medical Art (<http://smart.servier.com/>).

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2022.113518](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2022.113518).

References

- [1] K.D. Deane, Can rheumatoid arthritis be prevented? *Best. Pr. Res Clin. Rheuma* 27 (4) (2013), 467–85.
- [2] A.F. Radu, S.G. Bungau, Management of Rheumatoid Arthritis: An Overview, *Cells* 10 (2021) 11.
- [3] V.M. Holers, M.K. Demouelle, K.A. Kuhn, J.H. Buckner, W.H. Robinson, Y. Okamoto, et al., Rheumatoid arthritis and the mucosal origins hypothesis: protection turns to destruction, *Nat. Rev. Rheuma* 14 (9) (2018), 542–57.
- [4] C.S. Guerreiro, A. Calado, J. Sousa, J.E. Diet Fonseca, Microbiota, and gut permeability—the unknown triad in rheumatoid arthritis, *Front Med. (Lausanne)* 5 (2018) 349.
- [5] S.G. Bungau, T. Behl, A. Singh, A. Sehgal, S. Singh, S. Chigurupati, et al., Targeting probiotics in rheumatoid arthritis, *Nutrients* 13 (2021) 10.
- [6] T. Behl, K. Mehta, A. Sehgal, S. Singh, N. Sharma, A. Ahmadi, et al., Exploring the role of polyphenols in rheumatoid arthritis, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 62 (19) (2022) 5372–5393.
- [7] X.J. Chu, N.W. Cao, H.Y. Zhou, X. Meng, B. Guo, H.Y. Zhang, et al., The oral and gut microbiome in rheumatoid arthritis patients: a systematic review, *Rheumatol. (Oxf.)* 60 (3) (2021) 1054–1066.
- [8] N. Mena-Vázquez, P. Ruiz-Limón, I. Moreno-Indias, S. Manrique-Ariza, F. J. Tinahones, A. Fernández-Nebro, Expansion of rare and harmful lineages is associated with established rheumatoid arthritis, *J. Clin. Med.* 9 (2020) 4.
- [9] J.U. Scher, C. Ubeda, A. Artacho, M. Attur, S. Isaac, S.M. Reddy, et al., Decreased bacterial diversity characterizes the altered gut microbiota in patients with psoriatic arthritis, resembling dysbiosis in inflammatory bowel disease, *Arthritis Rheuma* 67 (1) (2015) 128–139.
- [10] A.I. Catrina, K.D. Deane, J.U. Scher, Gene, environment, microbiome and mucosal immune tolerance in rheumatoid arthritis, *Rheumatol. (Oxf.)* 55 (3) (2016) 391–402.
- [11] J. Chen, K. Wright, J.M. Davis, P. Jeraldo, E.V. Marietta, J. Murray, et al., An expansion of rare lineage intestinal microbes characterizes rheumatoid arthritis, *Genome Med* 8 (1) (2016) 43.
- [12] Y. Jeong, J.W. Kim, H.J. You, S.J. Park, J. Lee, J.H. Ju, et al., Gut microbial composition and function are altered in patients with early rheumatoid arthritis, *J. Clin. Med* 8 (2019) 5.
- [13] X. Zhang, D. Zhang, H. Jia, Q. Feng, D. Wang, D. Liang, et al., The oral and gut microbiomes are perturbed in rheumatoid arthritis and partly normalized after treatment, *Nat. Med.* 21 (8) (2015) 895–905.
- [14] A. Picchianti-Diamanti, C. Panebianco, S. Salemi, M.L. Sorgi, R. Di Rosa, A. Tropea, et al., Analysis of gut microbiota in rheumatoid arthritis patients: disease-related dysbiosis and modifications induced by etanercept, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 19 (2018) 10.
- [15] D. Aletaha, T. Neogi, A.J. Silman, J. Funovits, D.T. Felson, C.O. Bingham 3rd, et al., Rheumatoid arthritis classification criteria: an American College of Rheumatology/European League Against Rheumatism collaborative initiative, *Arthritis Rhe* 62 (9) (2010) eum. 2010, 2569–81.
- [16] W.H.O. Obesity, Preventing and Managing the Global Epidemic. Contract No, WHO, Geneva, 1997.
- [17] G. Mancia, G. De Backer, A. Dominiczak, R. Cifkova, R. Fagard, G. Germano, et al., ESH/ESC 2007 Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension, *Rev. Esp. Cardiol.* 60 (9) (2007), 968.e1–94.
- [18] Diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus, *Diabetes Care* 33 (Suppl 1) (2010), S62–9.
- [19] N. Iwamoto, A. Kawakami, K. Fujikawa, T. Aramaki, S.Y. Kawashiri, M. Tamai, et al., Prediction of DAS28-ESR remission at 6 months by baseline variables in patients with rheumatoid arthritis treated with etanercept in Japanese population, *Mod. Rheuma* 19 (5) (2009) 488–492.
- [20] J.R. Greenmyer, J.M. Stacy, A.E. Sahnoun, J.R. Beal, E. Diri, DAS28-CRP cutoffs for high disease activity and remission are lower than DAS28-ESR in rheumatoid arthritis, *ACR Open Rheuma* 2 (9) (2020) 507–511.
- [21] L. Fraenkel, J.M. Bathon, B.R. England St, E.W. Clair, T. Arayssi, K. Carandang, et al., American College of Rheumatology Guideline for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)* 73 (7) (2021) 924–939.
- [22] R.M. Fleischmann, D. van der Heijde, P.V. Gardiner, A. Szumski, L. Marshall, E.D. A.S.28-C.R.P. Bananis, and DAS28-ESR cut-offs for high disease activity in rheumatoid arthritis are not interchangeable, *RMD Open* 3 (1) (2017), e000382.
- [23] R. Fleischmann, D. van der Heijde, A.S. Koenig, R. Pedersen, A. Szumski, L. Marshall, et al., How much does Disease Activity Score in 28 joints ESR and CRP calculations underestimate disease activity compared with the Simplified Disease Activity Index? *Ann. Rheum. Dis.* 74 (6) (2015) 1132–1137.
- [24] E. Bolyen, J.R. Rideout, M.R. Dillon, N.A. Bokulich, C.C. Abnet, G.A. Al-Ghalith, et al., Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible microbiome data science using QIIME 2, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 37 (2019) 852–857.
- [25] G.M. Douglas, V.J. Maffei, J.R. Zaneveld, S.N. Yurgel, J.R. Brown, C.M. Taylor, et al., PICRUSt2 for prediction of metagenome functions, *Nat. Biotechnol.* 38 (2020) 685–688.
- [26] R. Caspi, R. Billington, I.M. Keseler, A. Kothari, M. Krummenacker, P.E. Midford, et al., The MetaCyc database of metabolic pathways and enzymes - a 2019 update, *Nucleic Acids Res.* 48 (D1) (2020) D445–d53.
- [27] D.H. Parks, G.W. Tyson, P. Hugenholtz, R.G. Beiko, STAMP: statistical analysis of taxonomic and functional profiles, *Bioinformatics* 30 (21) (2014) 3123–3124.
- [28] S. Mandal, W. Van Treuren, R.A. White, M. Eggesbø, R. Knight, S.D. Peddada, Analysis of composition of microbiomes: a novel method for studying microbial composition, *Micro Ecol. Health Dis.* 26 (2015) 27663.
- [29] H. Tsuji, K. Yano, M. Furu, N. Yamakawa, K. Ikari, M. Hashimoto, et al., Time-averaged disease activity fits better joint destruction in rheumatoid arthritis, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (1) (2017) 5856.
- [30] S. Manrique-Ariza, N. Mena-Vazquez, I. Ureña, J. Rioja, P. Valdivielso, L. Ginel-Mendoza, et al., Cumulative inflammatory burden and obesity as determinants of insulin resistance in patients with established rheumatoid arthritis: cross-sectional study, *BMJ Open* 11 (2) (2021), e044749.
- [31] A. Filipowicz-Sosnowska, R. Rupiński, Elderly onset rheumatoid arthritis, *Pol. Arch. Med. Wewn.* 118 (Suppl) (2008) 36–42.
- [32] N. Spinel-Bejarano, G. Quintana, R. Heredia, J.J. Yunis, J.E. Caminos, M.F. Garcés, et al., Comparative study of elderly-onset rheumatoid arthritis and young-onset rheumatoid arthritis in a Colombian population: clinical, laboratory and HLA-DRB1 findings, *Clin. Exp. Rheuma* 31 (1) (2013) 40–46.
- [33] Y. Ke, X. Dai, D. Xu, J. Liang, Y. Yu, H. Cao, et al., Features and outcomes of elderly rheumatoid arthritis: does the age of onset matter? A comparative study from a single center in China, *Rheuma Ther.* 8 (1) (2021), 243–54.
- [34] D.Y. Chen, T.Y. Hsieh, Y.M. Chen, C.W. Hsieh, J.L. Lan, F.J. Lin, Proinflammatory cytokine profiles of patients with elderly-onset rheumatoid arthritis: a comparison with younger-onset disease, *Gerontology* 55 (3) (2009) 250–258.
- [35] S. Lillegraven, T.K. Kvien, Measuring disability and quality of life in established rheumatoid arthritis, *Best. Pr. Res Clin. Rheuma* 21 (5) (2007) 827–840.
- [36] S. Norton, B. Fu, D.L. Scott, C. Deighton, D.P. Symmons, A.J. Wailoo, et al., Health Assessment Questionnaire disability progression in early rheumatoid arthritis: systematic review and analysis of two inception cohorts, *Semin Arthritis Rheum.* 44 (2) (2014), 131–44.
- [37] Y. Pan, S. Norton, J.M. Gwinnutt, L. Kearsley-Fleet, D.P.M. Symmons, M. Lunt, et al., Not all moderate disease is the same - identification of disability trajectories among patients with rheumatoid arthritis and moderate disease activity, *PLoS One* 14 (5) (2019), e0215999.
- [38] B. Combe, I. Logeart, M.C. Belkacemi, S. Dadoun, T. Schaefferbeke, J.P. Daurès, et al., Comparison of the long-term outcome for patients with rheumatoid arthritis with persistent moderate disease activity or disease remission during the first year after diagnosis: data from the ESPOIR cohort, *Ann. Rheum. Dis.* 74 (4) (2015) 724–729.
- [39] Y. Jeong, J. Jhun, S.Y. Lee, H.S. Na, J. Choi, K.H. Cho, et al., Therapeutic potential of a novel bifidobacterium identified through microbiome profiling of RA patients with different RF levels, *Front Immunol.* 12 (2021), 736196.
- [40] X.O. Yang, B.P. Pappu, R. Nurieva, A. Akimzhanov, H.S. Kang, Y. Chung, et al., T helper 17 lineage differentiation is programmed by orphan nuclear receptors ROR alpha and ROR gamma, *Immunity* 28 (1) (2008) 29–39.
- [41] J. Chen, K. Wright, J.M. Davis, P. Jeraldo, E.V. Marietta, J. Murray, et al., An expansion of rare lineage intestinal microbes characterizes rheumatoid arthritis, *Genome Med.* 8 (2016).
- [42] C. Picard, J. Fioramonti, A. Francois, T. Robinson, F. Neant, C. Matuchansky, Review article: bifidobacteria as probiotic agents – physiological effects and clinical benefits, *Aliment Pharm. Ther.* 22 (6) (2005) 495–512.

- [43] M. Asquith, P.R. Sternes, M.E. Costello, L. Karstens, S. Diamond, T.M. Martin, et al., HLA alleles associated with risk of ankylosing spondylitis and rheumatoid arthritis influence the gut microbiome, *Arthritis Rheuma* 71 (10) (2019) 1642–1650.
- [44] P. López, B. de Paz, J. Rodríguez-Carrio, A. Hevia, B. Sánchez, A. Margolles, et al., Th17 responses and natural IgM antibodies are related to gut microbiota composition in systemic lupus erythematosus patients, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 24072.
- [45] H. Siddiqui, T. Chen, A. Aliko, P.M. Mydel, R. Jonsson, I. Olsen, Microbiological and bioinformatics analysis of primary Sjogren's syndrome patients with normal salivation, *J. Oral. Microbiol.* 8 (2016) 31119.
- [46] A. Kurilshikov, C. Medina-Gomez, R. Bacigalupe, D. Radjabzadeh, J. Wang, A. Demirkan, et al., Large-scale association analyses identify host factors influencing human gut microbiome composition, *Nat. Genet* 53 (2) (2021) 156–165.
- [47] B.J. Parker, P.A. Wearsch, A.C.M. Veloo, A. Rodríguez-Palacios, The genus *Alistipes*: gut bacteria with emerging implications to inflammation, cancer, and mental health, *Front Immunol.* 11 (2020) 906.
- [48] I. Cornejo-Pareja, P. Ruiz-Limón, A.M. Gómez-Pérez, M. Molina-Vega, I. Moreno-Indias, F.J. Tinahones, Differential microbial pattern description in subjects with autoimmune-based thyroid diseases: a pilot study, *J. Pers. Med.* 10 (2020) 4.
- [49] V.K. Gupta, K.Y. Cunningham, B. Hur, U. Bakshi, H. Huang, K.J. Warrington, et al., Gut microbial determinants of clinically important improvement in patients with rheumatoid arthritis, *Genome Med.* 13 (1) (2021) 149.
- [50] D. Takahashi, N. Hoshina, Y. Kabumoto, Y. Maeda, A. Suzuki, H. Tanabe, et al., Microbiota-derived butyrate limits the autoimmune response by promoting the differentiation of follicular regulatory T cells, *EBioMedicine* 58 (2020), 102913.
- [51] B. Chen, Y. Zhao, S. Li, L. Yang, H. Wang, T. Wang, et al., Variations in oral microbiome profiles in rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis with potential biomarkers for arthritis screening, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (1) (2018) 17126.
- [52] S. Priya, M.B. Burns, T. Ward, R.A.T. Mars, B. Adamowicz, E.F. Lock, et al., Identification of shared and disease-specific host gene-microbiome associations across human diseases using multi-omic integration, *Nat. Microbiol.* (2022).
- [53] C.G. Boer, D. Radjabzadeh, C. Medina-Gomez, S. Garmeva, D. Schiphof, P. Arp, et al., Intestinal microbiome composition and its relation to joint pain and inflammation, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (1) (2019) 4881.
- [54] J.S. Lee, R.X. Wang, M.S. Goldberg, G.P. Clifford, D.J. Kao, S.P. Colgan, Microbiota-sourced purines support wound healing and mucous barrier function, *iScience* 23 (6) (2020), 101226.
- [55] J. Clarke, Disease onset goes with its gut in RA, *Nat. Rev. Rheuma* 16 (7) (2020) 350.
- [56] E. Lurz, R.G. Horne, P. Määttänen, R.Y. Wu, S.R. Botts, B. Li, et al., Vitamin B12 deficiency alters the gut microbiota in a murine model of colitis, *Front Nutr.* 7 (2020) 83.
- [57] P. Barcellos-de-Souza, J.A. Moraes, J.C. de-Freitas-Junior, J.A. Morgado-Díaz, C. Barja-Fidalgo, M.A. Arruda, Heme modulates intestinal epithelial cell activation: involvement of NADPHox-derived ROS signaling, *Am. J. Physiol. Cell Physiol.* 304 (2) (2013) C170–C179.
- [58] D.E. Matei, M. Menon, D.G. Alber, A.M. Smith, B. Nedjat-Shokouhi, A. Fasano, et al., Intestinal barrier dysfunction plays an integral role in arthritis pathology and can be targeted to ameliorate disease, *Med (N.Y)* 2 (7) (2021), 864-883.e9.
- [59] Y. Maeda, K. Takeda, Host-microbiota interactions in rheumatoid arthritis, *Exp. Mol. Med.* 51 (12) (2019) 1–6.
- [60] K. Terato, T. Waritani, R. Fukai, H. Shionoya, H. Itoh, K. Katayama, Contribution of bacterial pathogens to evoking serological disease markers and aggravating disease activity in rheumatoid arthritis, *PLoS One* 13 (2) (2018), e0190588.
- [61] Y. Kinashi, K. Hase, Partners in leaky gut syndrome: intestinal dysbiosis and autoimmunity, *Front Immunol.* 12 (2021), 673708.